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PROPOSING AUTOMATED REGRESSION SUITE USING OPEN SOURCE TOOLS FOR A HEALTH CARE SOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

Regression testing is very important for the delivery of high quality product. It helps to simulate a suite of critical test cases periodically and helps to identify if introduction of any new features or any source code change has adversely affected the software quality or functionality. As a result, regression testing cannot be ignored from the software testing life cycle (STLC). But just doing a regression testing cannot be beneficial until it is accompanied by automation testing. Automated regression suite not only saves time and cost by re-running test scripts again and again but it also provide the confidence that all the critical test cases has been covered, providing more confidence in the quality of the product and increasing the ability to meet schedules. IT has an ability to explore the whole software every day without requiring much of manual effort. Current software is going through continuous development which requires testing again and again to check if new feature implementation has affected the existing functionality. In addition to this, it is facing issue in validation of the installation at client site and requires availability of testers to check the critical functionality of the software manually. This paper came up with the solution of creating automated regression suite for the software. The current research will provide guidelines to the future researchers on how to create an automated regression suite for any web application using open source tools.

KEYWORDS

Automation testing, Regression testing, Visual Studio, C#, Selenium Webdriver, Agile- Scrum Methodology, Health care solution, Visual SVN, Trello

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QUALITY ASSESSMENT MODEL OF THE ADAPTIVE GUIDANCE

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ABSTRACT

The need for adaptive guidance systems is now recognized for all software development processes. The new needs generated by the mobility context for software development led these guidance systems to both quality and ability adaptation to the possible variations of the development context. This paper deals with the adaptive guidance quality to satisfy the developer's guidance needs. We propose a quality model to the adaptive guidance. This model offers a more detailed description of the quality factors of guidance service adaptation. This description aims to assess the quality level of each guidance adaptation factor and therefore the evaluation of the adaptive quality guidance service.

KEYWORDS

Quality model, Guidance system quality, Adaptive guidance, Plasticity.

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AN APPLICATION OF PHYSICS EXPERIMENTS OF HIGH SCHOOL BY USING AUGMENTED REALITY

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ABSTRACT

There has been done little research to validate the utility and usability of virtual and augmented reality environments. The evaluation of usability of these new technologies is very important to design systems that are more intuitive than a traditional method. Such an evaluation is also important for future development of applications that can gain from this new technology. The augmented reality (AR) is a technology that embedded virtual object (video, picture and 3D object) to the user view the real world. The combination of AR technology with the educational content creates new type of automated applications and acts to enhance the effectiveness and attractiveness of teaching and learning for students in real life scenarios. The study aims to improve the teaching methods used in secondary school by employing modern educational technology and thus assess the effectiveness of AR apps in teaching students the physics experiments. Therefore, in this study we took the challenge of adapting this technology to facilitate physics subject in secondary school.

KEYWORDS

Augmented Reality, Physics, Education, System, Students, Teachers, Technology, Mobile, Lab, Virtual Reality

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ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOFTWARE COMPLEXITY AND SECURITY

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ABSTRACT

This work aims at discussing the complexity aspect of software while demonstrating its relationship with security. Complexity is an essential part of software; however, numerous studies indicate that they increase the vulnerability of the software systems and introduce bugs in the program. Many developers face difficulty when trying to understand the complex components of software. Complexity in software increases when objects in the software are used to design a more complex object while creating a hierarchical complexity in the system. However, it is necessary for the developers to strive for minimum complexity, as increased complexity introduces security risks in the software, which can cause severe monetary and reputational damage to a government or a private organization. It even causes bodily harm to human beings with various examples found in previous years where security breaches led to severe consequences. Hence it is vital to maintain low complexity and simple design of structure. Various developers tend to introduce deliberate complexities in the system so that they do not have to write the same program twice; however, it is getting problematic for the software organizations as the demands of security are continually increasing.

KEYWORDS

Software security, Software complexity, Software quality

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STRUCTURAL COMPLEXITY ATTRIBUTE CLASSIFICATION FRAMEWORK (SCACF) FOR SASSY CASCADING STYLE SHEETS

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ABSTRACT

Several researchers have proposed the various classes of software attributes to guide in the derivation of metrics for software products. These existing classifications have targeted traditional software paradigms such as procedural and object-oriented software. Sassy cascading style sheets (SCSS) has unique features since it combines Cascading style sheets (CSS) features with traditional software features such as variables, functions and control flows. Due to this uniqueness, there arises a need to develop a new classification scheme that can be effectively used to classify all the possible structural attributes for Sassy cascading style sheets. The aim of this paper, therefore, is to develop and validate a comprehensive software complexity attributes classification framework for SCSS. The new framework was validated through an online expert opinion survey, where thirteen SCSS experts were involved. Results show that the proposed framework is complete and effective to guide metrics researchers in defining new metrics for SCSS

KEYWORDS

Cascading Style Sheets, SCSS Complexity classification framework., Software attributes, Structural complexity

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